

Using Multimodal Machine Learning to Distant View the Illustrated World of the Illustrated London News, 1842-1900

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On 14 May 1842, the publication of the first issue of the weekly periodical Illustrated London News (ILN) helped usher in the age of visual mass media. For the first time in history, a periodical not only regularly described current events but also used illustrations to depict them. The ILN quickly became a staple of Victorian life, achieving a circulation of 300.000 copies by 1863 (Smits, 2020). Researchers have analyzed its pages to study British identity (McKendry, 1994; Sinnema, 1998), the British Empire (Boyer, 2002; Smits, 2017), new technology (Dobraszczyk, 2005; Fyfe, 2013), and many other topics. While the visual world of the ILN was marked by the sheer number of illustrations it published, the majority of these studies depend on close reading of a select number of illustrations. This paper shows that recently developed multimodal machine learning models can be used to ‘distant view’ (Arnold and Tilton, 2019) the visual world of the ILN. It presents the first two steps of our larger project Distant Viewing the Illustrated London News: (1) we use the Newspaper Navigator model to extract visual content from the digitized pages of the periodical; and (2) apply the multimodal machine learning model CLIP to identify images of ‘steamships’ and ‘the army’ in a sample of 874 illustrations. We also use the model to quickly add metadata to this sample, identifying all the maps in the 874 images.

Historians have used computer vision techniques to analyze collections of digitized images (Wevers and Smits, 2020). Because they were trained to identify a select number of objects in modern high-definition photographs, applying these techniques to nineteenth-century line engravings presents a ‘formidable challenge’ (Fyfe and Ge, 2018). Recently introduced multimodal machine learning models are optimized to connect texts to images and vice versa. As a result, even without task- or data-specific training, multimodal models can be applied to a wide variety of ‘text to image’ and ‘image to text’ classification tasks in heterogeneous datasets (Radford et al., 2021).

In the first step of our project, we produced a sample of Gale’s Illustrated London News Historical Archive. We selected two issues per year between 1842 and 1900, when the publication largely switched from publishing illustrations to photographs. We

extracted visual content from these 1151 pages by feeding them through the Newspaper Navigator (NN) model (Lee et al., 2020), which was trained on early twentieth-century digitized newspapers to recognize seven categories (ads, comics, editorial cartoons, headlines, illustrations, maps, and photographs). While NN reliably identified illustrations, it frequently misclassified them. For our sample, we combined 874 illustrations, which were classified as comics, editorial cartoons, illustrations, maps, and photographs.

Subsequently, we applied CLIP (Radford et al., 2021) to extract embeddings of the 874 images. CLIP connects images to text(s) by calculating the cosine similarity between images and textual embeddings. This means that we can link our 874 illustrations to any textual prompt, enabling us to use textual queries to search for visual concepts. Concerning the text-to-image task, we can search for straightforward visual concepts, such as ‘a steamship’ (Figure 1). However, because CLIP has learned to connect text to images, we can also retrieve more complex visual concepts, such as ‘an image of the army’ (Figure 2). Without having to (manually) add metadata, CLIP allows us to search a large collection of images in the same way that OCR allows keyword searches in large collections of texts. Earlier work showed that CLIP can also be used to quickly add metadata to images (Smits and Kestemont, 2021). Hoping to analyze the imperial geography of the ILN in a later stage of our project, we connected the 874 images to the prompt ‘a map’ (Figure 3). Because the Newspaper Navigator model also searches for maps, we can compare its performance to CLIP. While both models identified the same four true positives, the application of NN led to 34 false positives.

Combing the OLR capabilities of NN with CLIP allows us to distant view the illustrated world of the ILN. In future work, we will improve the performance of NN by retraining it on the pages of the ILN and further explore the capabilities of CLIP by testing its performance on an annotated set of illustrations. More generally, this paper demonstrated the so-called zero-shot capability of multimodal machine learning models on heterogeneous historical visual data (Smits and Wevers, 2023). Without task- or data-specific training, CLIP can be used to quickly explore and analyze historical visual data at scale.

Fig 1: Top-4 cosine similarity scores (0.324/0.312/0.306/0.306) for the prompt ‘a steamship’ in our sample.

Fig 2: Top-4 cosine similarity scores (0.299/0.297/0.289/0.285) for the prompt 'an image of the army' in our sample.

Fig 3: Connecting the 874 images in our sample to the prompt 'a map'.

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